

THE RIGHTS AND TASKS OF THE PROSECUTOR IN THE CRIMINAL PROCESS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND GERMANY

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Abstract: this article is devoted to the rights and tasks of the prosecutor in the criminal process of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Germany, the main task of the prosecutor's office is to carry out criminal prosecution and support the prosecution in court.

Keywords: prosecutor, rights and tasks, lack of supervisory functions.

The Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the status of a prosecutor as follows: "a prosecutor is an official authorized, within the limits of his competence, to carry out criminal prosecution on behalf of the State during criminal proceedings, as well as supervision of the procedural activities of the bodies of inquiry and the bodies of preliminary investigation." A prosecutor is a concept that covers the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan, prosecutors subordinate to him, their deputies and other officials of the prosecutor's office participating in criminal proceedings and endowed with appropriate powers by the federal Law on the Prosecutor's Office and the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (paragraph 31, Article 5 of the CPC of the Republic of Uzbekistan). The legal basis for their implementation is the Federal Law "On the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan", other federal laws, as well as regulations of the Prosecutor General's Office. Thus, the main activities of the prosecutor in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as a participant in the criminal process, are – the implementation of criminal prosecution and supervision of the activities of investigative bodies; state prosecution.

The constitutions of foreign countries, which include the Federal Republic of Germany, pay very little attention to the legal status of the Prosecutor's office as a whole. This is explained by the fact that the prosecutor's office is not considered here as a separate system of bodies, but as part of the judicial or executive power.

The main task of the German Prosecutor's Office is to carry out criminal prosecution. She has the right to establish the circumstances of the case, collect evidence, make a decision on the end of the investigation (par. 160 of the CPC), in addition, the prosecutor interrogates the accused, witnesses, expert; orders the police to conduct a search, seizure of material evidence and other actions.

The main task of the German Prosecutor's Office is to carry out criminal prosecution. She has the right to determine the circumstances of the case, collect evidence, make a decision on the end of the investigation (par. 160 of the CPC), in addition, the prosecutor interrogates the accused, witnesses, expert; orders the police to conduct a search, seizure of material evidence and other actions. The Prosecutor's Office may complete the investigation by filing a public lawsuit with the indictment, or terminate the case.

The prosecutor has the right and duty to participate in the main trial, to make protests against the judge's decision, to carry out actions to enforce the court's decision. In addition, in Germany, criminal prosecution can be carried out by "auxiliary employees of the prosecutor's office." Officials of various levels can carry out the initial collection of information. These are representatives of the security police, the criminal police, as well as a number of officials of other state bodies. The list of categories of employees who are given the status of "auxiliary employees (officials) of the Federal Prosecutor's Office" is established by the land Government or land justice authorities. Among the police services, these categories of persons have broad powers to conduct investigations under the direction of the Prosecutor's Office.

It is quite appropriate to refer to the status of the prosecutor in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the powers of the prosecutor in the Republic of Uzbekistan today look ambiguous.

The primary function of the prosecutor in the criminal process of Uzbekistan should also be designated the implementation of criminal prosecution on behalf of the state, since it is carried out by the prosecutor, both at the pre-trial and at the judicial stage of the criminal process. Further, Article 37 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan gives the prosecutor the function of supervising the preliminary investigation bodies, this function is primarily carried out at the pre-trial stage of the criminal process, but it also takes place at the judicial stages. The activity of the preliminary investigation bodies is expressed in procedural and investigative documents that make up the materials of the criminal case and the prosecutor continues to carry out his function in the judicial stages, for example, on the exclusion of inadmissible evidence.

One of the most important functions in accordance with Part 3 of Article 37 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the function of public prosecution in court proceedings. Speaking about the function of supervision, it should be pointed out that the prosecutor performs another

function during the trial – supervision of the exercise of Constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens of Uzbekistan.

To determine the criminal-legal functions of the prosecutor, it is necessary to refer to Article 37 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Law "On the Prosecutor's Office", as well as to the Criminal Procedure Code of Germany 2012. The primary function of the prosecutor in the criminal process of both states should be designated the implementation of criminal prosecution on behalf of the state, since it is carried out by prosecutors both at pre-trial and judicial stages criminal proceedings.

The activity of the preliminary investigation bodies is expressed in procedural and investigative documents that make up the materials of the criminal case and the prosecutor continues to carry out his function in the judicial stages, for example, by filing a petition for the exclusion of inadmissible evidence (on the example of the Republic of Uzbekistan). One of the most important tasks is also the maintenance of state prosecution in court proceedings (Article 37 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan). In the Federal Republic of Germany, the prosecutor has the right and obligation to participate in the main trial (par. 226 of the Criminal Procedure Code of Germany), and Article 227 of the Criminal Procedure Code of Germany indicates that several officials of the prosecutor's office have the right to participate and distribute duties among themselves in the main trial. The prosecutor has the right to make a protest against the judge's decision. Article 296 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Federal Republic of Germany recognizes that it is permissible to carry out actions to enforce a court decision, and also indicates an appeal against court decisions.

Despite the fact that "procedural law as a set of legal norms regulating the jurisdictional and other protective activities of specially authorized state bodies appeared only at relatively late stages of human society"⁵, in the Federal Republic of Germany, the offset of the term of detention in a foreign State falls under its competence. In accordance with Article 450 of the Criminal Procedure Code of Germany, Part 3, the court, at the request of the prosecutor's office, may rule that the offset is not fully or partially made if it is not justified in connection with the behavior of the convicted person after the verdict, in which the factual circumstances of the case were last checked.

It should be noted that the German Prosecutor's Office, in accordance with Article 451, can act as an agency for the execution of criminal penalties. Thus, it can be concluded that the organization of the activities of the Prosecutor's office

in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Federal Republic of Germany has similar features. So in Germany, the prosecutor's office manages the activities of the judicial police, supports the prosecution in court, carries out criminal prosecution at all stages of criminal proceedings.

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